

THE ROLE OF INTERACTIVE AND VISUAL MEDIA IN TEACHING PHYSICS

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Abstract. *This article explores the role of interactive and visual tools in teaching physics, particularly in molecular physics and thermodynamics. It presents the integration of PhET and Algodoo platforms into the educational process.*

Keywords: *interactive learning, visual tools, simulation, physics education, PhET, Algodoo.*

Introduction

In today's era of globalization, one of the most pressing issues facing the education system is the formation of deep knowledge, practical skills and competencies in students. In particular, traditional approaches to teaching natural sciences, especially physics, are losing their effectiveness. The richness of physics with complex theoretical models often hinders students' understanding of the subject. Therefore, the use of modern pedagogical technologies, in particular, the integration of interactive and visual tools into the educational process, is becoming increasingly important.

World experience shows that in lessons taught using interactive methods, the level of student learning is 30–40% higher. This is especially emphasized in the World Bank's 2022 "Technology in Education" report. Advanced countries such as Estonia, Singapore, and Finland have managed to develop analytical thinking in students by introducing simulation, virtual laboratory, and AR/VR technologies in their schools. Such approaches form students not only as knowledge, but also as personnel capable of solving real problems.

The Republic of Uzbekistan is also carrying out consistent reforms in this regard. In particular, the Presidential Decrees set the task of improving the quality of continuous education, creating modern educational resources, and training competitive specialists through the integration of disciplines. Organizing lessons based on simulations, video animations, and visual graphics to make physics interesting and understandable to students significantly increases the quality of education. In this regard, it is extremely important to use the capabilities of interactive platforms such as PhET and Algodoo.

This article deeply analyzes the role of such interactive and visual tools in physics education, their effectiveness, place in world experience, and scientific and theoretical foundations. The impact of interactive technologies on the effectiveness of lessons is highlighted on the example of topics such as molecular physics and thermodynamics. In addition, attention is paid to the role of visual tools in consolidating theoretical knowledge among students and forming their skills in relating it to real life.

1. Theoretical foundations of interactive and visual tools

In modern educational methodology, the concept of interactivity refers to an educational process based on active interaction between the student and the teacher. Interactive methods

involve students directly, rather than indirectly, in the educational process. This approach, based on Vygotsky's sociocultural theory, emphasizes the formation of knowledge with the active participation of the student, in a social context. An interactive learning environment is an environment in which the student thinks independently, asks questions, analyzes and draws conclusions. This process is especially important in physics, which is saturated with complex theoretical models.

The theoretical foundations of visual tools are based on the role of visual perception and memory in the student in pedagogical psychology. According to Dual Coding Theory (Paivio, 1986), knowledge is processed through visual and verbal channels, and visual information is usually remembered faster and longer. For this reason, explaining concepts and laws through visual representations such as graphics, animations, and simulations in physics lessons reduces the student's cognitive load and helps them consciously master the subject.

1-table

Types of interactive and visual aids and their role in physics education

Tool Type	Example (platform or tool)	Description	Educational function
Simulation	PhET, Algodoo	Allows modeling of physical phenomena in a digital environment	Visual presentation of theory, safe experiments
Graphics and Diagrams	Boyle-Mariott graph, graphs	Graphs and drawings that visually represent concepts	Simplification of complex information
Video and Animation	YouTube lessons, Khan Academy	Demonstrative materials that show physical processes in action	Clear and complete communication of dynamic concepts
Virtual Lab	Labster, PhET	A tool that allows you to perform experiments in a virtual environment	Strengthening practical skills, safe experiments
Online Tests	Kahoot, Quizizz	Interactive tests that test knowledge	Controlling knowledge, determining the level
Interactive Tutorials	EduPage, BilimLand	Digital learning resources that combine text, graphics, audio and video materials	Supporting independent learning, forming an individual educational path

In addition, according to the theory of constructivism, knowledge is formed by a person based on his own experience. According to this theory, the student acquires not ready-made knowledge, but a model of knowledge that he has built himself. Many topics in physics - heat transfer, molecular motion, pressure changes - are understood through direct experimentation or modeling. Therefore, interactive simulations such as PhET or Algodoo are suitable for a constructive approach, turning the student into an active learning subject.

From the point of view of the cognitive approach, interactive and visual tools attract the attention of students, increase their motivation, and allow them to deeply master the educational material in a short time. Numerous scientific studies (Mayer, 2001; Clark & Mayer, 2016) have

shown that lessons enriched with interactive tools are 1.5–2 times more effective than the usual lecture method. This approach is especially effective in STEM subjects.

2. Foreign experience and platforms

In recent years, digital and interactive technologies have been widely introduced in the education system of developed countries in teaching STEM subjects, including physics. According to the World Bank's 2022 report "Technology in Education", lessons taught using interactive tools increase the level of students' mastery of science by an average of 30-40%. These methods are especially effective in understanding abstract topics such as molecular physics and thermodynamics.

In advanced countries such as Estonia, Singapore and Finland, virtual laboratories, simulation tools and AR/VR technologies are actively used in physics lessons starting from the school level. For example, in Singapore, topics such as the "ideal gas model", "thermal conductivity", "light interference" in physics are studied independently outside the laboratory environment through PhET and simplified Java applets. This allows each student to perform the experiment individually, which increases activity.

PhET Interactive Simulations is a free online platform created by the University of Colorado, USA, that allows you to visually and interactively model various processes in physics (heat transfer, molecular motion, pressure changes, etc.). The advantage of this platform is its simple interface, the fact that the experiments are based on real physical laws, and the availability of interface options in the Uzbek language.

Ideal Gas

Figure 1. Ideal gas simulation on the PhET platform

Algodo is a physics simulation program developed in Sweden, primarily intended for school students, that allows interactive control of processes such as the motion of objects, gravity, collisions, and fluid flow. The program creates a physical environment using the drag-and-drop

function and monitors the results of the action in real time. Algodoo is especially convenient for conducting interactive lessons in primary and secondary education.

Figure 2. Fluid movement on the Algodoo platform

Also, in the Finnish education system, physics education is organized on the basis of an individual approach through digital resources such as EduLab, in Norway - ExploreLearning, and in Korea - Learning Management System (LMS). In these countries, special "interactive content development courses" have been established for teachers, and teachers are trained to independently create their own teaching materials in digital format. As a result, the student is formed not only as a learner, but also as an active participant, analyst and solution-finder.

3. Integrated approach in physics education

Physics is not only a set of theoretical concepts, but also a practical science that explains natural phenomena and technologies. Therefore, in the modern education system, physics must be taught in close integration with other disciplines. An integrated approach expands the student's knowledge and helps to understand the interrelationships between different disciplines. Especially since departments such as molecular physics and thermodynamics are directly and inextricably linked to mathematics, chemistry and biology, it is of great importance to establish bridges with these disciplines in the educational process.

The scientific and methodological basis of the integrated approach is based on the ideas of pedagogical theorists such as Vygotsky, Bruner, Piaget, Dewey. Their ideas on education emphasize that the transfer of knowledge not in an artificial way, but in an interconnected form in a whole system, deeply develops the student's thinking. For example, according to Vygotsky, the acquisition of knowledge is a social process, and this process takes place through communication, activity and cultural means. In physics, this is especially expressed through modeling and analysis.

The integration of physics and mathematics must be particularly strong, since the laws of physics are often expressed through mathematical models, equations and graphs. For example, mathematical formulas serve as the main tool for calculating the ideal gas equation or the amount

of heat. The student must be able to understand and work with the physical content and mathematical expression at the same time. This requires cross-subject integration.

Integration with chemistry is manifested in the study of topics such as the movement of molecules, pressure, temperature, and heat conductivity. In the department of molecular physics and thermodynamics, concepts such as changes in the state of matter, energy transfer, and heat capacity are related to reactions and energy balance in chemistry. Therefore, it is also necessary to explain to students the chemical foundations of physical processes.

Integration with biology is connected through the effects of heat and energy on living organisms, heat exchange in the human body, heart activity, and respiratory processes. For example, thermoregulation is a physiological process, but it is based on the 1st law of thermodynamics. Therefore, students must understand the natural connection between these disciplines.

Integration with information technology is an integral part of modern physics education. Students use algorithms to create physical simulations, analyze measurement results using spreadsheets, and process data using statistical methods. This provides them with the opportunity to connect with fields such as computer science, statistics, and technological design.

2-table

Integration of Physics with Other Sciences

Subject	Related topics in physics	Educational significance of integration
Mathematics	Equations, graphs, statistical analysis, physical models	Understanding physical formulas, strengthening quantitative calculations
Chemistry	Molecular motion, pressure, temperature, energy transfer	Relating thermodynamic concepts to chemical processes
Biology	Thermoregulation, heat transfer in the human body	Understanding the impact of physical laws on biological systems
Information Technology (IT)	Simulation, electronic computing, data analysis	Modeling physical experiments in a digital environment, analyzing results in real time
Technology and Engineering	Heat engines, mechanisms, energy cycles	Applying physical laws to real technical devices
Life Experience (Practice)	Refrigerators, air conditioners, transportation systems	Relating theoretical knowledge to everyday life phenomena, creating a learning environment close to life

Physics education should also be integrated with real-life experience. When theoretical knowledge in education is linked to everyday life events, it seems significant and relevant to the student. For example, the principle of operation of air conditioners, the processes inside a

refrigerator, the movement of pistons used in cars - all this is based on physical laws. Therefore, modeling and visualizing these processes using interactive tools helps to easily master them.

Scheme 1.

Interactive learning process model

In programs such as Erasmus+, funded by the European Union, an integrated approach is also identified as one of the priorities. In the “STEM Integration” models, students are developing problem-solving, innovative approaches, and teamwork skills through interdisciplinary lessons. Such approaches in physics education transform students from traditional learners into innovative solution-seekers.

Conclusion. *The effective use of interactive and visual tools in modern physics education develops students' deep understanding of the subject, independent thinking, and the ability to analyze real-life phenomena on a scientific basis. In teaching complex sections such as molecular physics and thermodynamics, interactive platforms such as PhET and Algodoo, in particular, enliven the educational process and increase students' motivation for the subject.*

The study found that the importance of visual tools (graphics, animations, video experiments) in consolidating theoretical knowledge is extremely high, as they activate students' thinking and significantly increase their memorization. Also, the knowledge acquired through tests, simulations, and virtual laboratories is stored in long-term memory and applied in practice.

By integrating physics with other disciplines - mathematics, chemistry, biology, technology, and IT - it is possible to broaden the student's worldview and teach them to analyze

problem situations from different perspectives. It is precisely interdisciplinary integration that forms modern competencies in students and provides knowledge related to real life.

Based on the above, it can be concluded that organizing physics education on the basis of an interactive and integrated approach and the comprehensive use of visual, digital, and experiential tools in education can achieve deep and effective mastery by students.

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